

INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article is developing day by day new innovative forms of education to the preschool education system and introduction of technologies, development of development strategy, edge establish pre-school educational organizations for the rural population of our country and creating conditions, the number of pre-school education coverage increase, every child receives excellent education and upbringing in preschool education reforms such as collective assistance are mentioned.

Keywords: education, upbringing, development, innovation, technology, harmonious generation.

"Speaking about the educational system, which is decisive in our lives, Abdullah Avlani has to repeat and repeat the wise thoughts of our grandfather: education is a matter of life-matter for us. What sphere we do not get, we cannot achieve any change, a comfortable life without training modern mature personnel. The preparation of such personnel, a healthy gene pool of the nation, first of all, begins with the preschool education system." Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan

The education system in our country has been fundamentally reformed and our tomorrow is worthy special attention to bringing up a competent generation who are successors being directed. To develop the preschool education system in 2017-2021 implementation of large-scale complex activities of the intended "Road Map". It is foreseen, and no less than any other generation. It is important for him to grow up to be healthy and highly spiritual is a document. It involves radically improving the level of preparing children for school, applying modern educational programs to the educational process, creation of necessary conditions for intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development is defined. As part of the program, 5-6-year-old children are prepared for school education. Extensive work has been done on the creation and development of alternative forms increased. Organization of short-term groups in state pre-school education organizations done. In such groups, various developmental for preschool children practical training is conducted. On this basis, more than 305

thousand 5-6 every year an opportunity to prepare a child for school education was created. In addition, 3-6-year-olds who are not included in preschool education providing parents of children with methodical manuals and with them an alternative to preparing for school education by conducting explanatory work system was also introduced. Using the experience of advanced foreign countries alternative programs for the preschool education system have been developed, put into practice. Updated programs bring children to school with better quality training, their intellectual ability and potential for logical thinking to upgrade, write and read better than before serves to learn. An alternative form of education and upbringing is preschool education and upbringing is a model of organization of the innovative educational process in the system.

Goals and tasks of organizing alternative forms of pre-school education.

- Increasing the level of coverage of children with quality preschool education.
- Children who are not covered by pre-school education have an advanced foreign experience taking into account all-round intellectual, moral, creating conditions for aesthetic and physical development.
- Quality preparation of children for primary education.
- Preschoolers living in remote areas and rural areas to ensure that children have equal rights and quality pre-school education.
- State and non-state preschool education organizations, preschool education a legal practitioner engaged in providing non-state educational services in the field strengthening the material and technical base of individuals.
- Formation of the foundations of the child's personality, development of interest in knowledge.
- Remote rural areas, mountainous districts, etc., where there is a possibility of MTT construction from low-cost, free quality pre-school education in difficult settlements ensure equal use.
- Development of the non-state sector of preschool education services. In neighborhoods with a need for pre-school education, including rural areas organization of alternative forms of pre-school education in places and their necessity it is envisaged to take measures to provide material and technical means. That's it the question arises: the capacity of state preschool educational organizations is children when the number is small, what can be seen as a solution? Ministers "One-year mandatory preparation of children for primary education 2018-2019 from the academic year in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Fergana region and compulsory free primary education for children in some districts of our capital a one-year training pilot project was implemented.

Implement the project a total of 494 groups were established to increase Experimental groups for children who do not attend preschool educational institutions assistance in pre-school education is necessary for this was organized in order to create conditions. The groups are state and non-state preschool educational institutions, non-state education in the field of preschool education was opened on the basis of legal entities providing services.

Training in experimental groups for 3-4 hours in one or two shifts process is organized. The number of children in one group should not exceed 30. — By the state where experimental groups are placed in preschool education educates and prepares children for school in accordance with established requirements. Children's characteristics are certainly taken into account.

To experimental groups, to preschool education organizations over 5 years old absent children are accepted. Compulsory primary education children who have passed the training are given a certificate of the state model. This alternative form of pre-school education is for a child who did not go to kindergarten to activate at the same level as his peers when he goes to the first grade prepares children for school education based on the planned program. So that's it is a form of education that is convenient for all parents and is protected by the state. 16 by MTV in the presentation of alternative forms of preschool education re-equipped buses, two parking lots with playgrounds and MTT with 2 modules was presented.

MTTs based on Isuzu HC 40 buses moves along the specified direction. Duration of stay in mobile groups.No more than 3 hours, maximum number of 16 children from 3 to 7 years old will be In order to make lessons interesting for all students, MTV specialists have developed a special program for different age groups,and the teachers have received appropriate training.

In conclusion, I can say that we will achieve our goal only when we make our young children interested in education from a young age and give them a perfect education. We should pay attention to the education of the young generation from childhood. Because we protect them from all kinds of bad things, habits, and events that appear in our time, and to prevent them from getting involved in such bad things in the future, while being very attentive to their education, the way to education is from childhood. I think it should be done.

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